

“Beyond Rules and Procedural Rationality”: Emotional Intelligence as a Remedy for Administrative Apathy in Public Administration

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ABSTRACT

In the contemporary public administration, administrative apathy manifested through indifference, procedural rigidity, and lack of responsiveness has emerged as a persistent governance challenge across public institutions, particularly in developing and nation which inherited colonial bureaucratic apparatus. Though classical and neoclassical theories of public administration have prioritised rules, hierarchy, and procedural rationality to ensure efficiency and accountability, these frameworks have often neglected the human and emotional dimensions of administrative behaviour leading to ecology of inhumane administration.

In the above context this paper argues that such neglect contributes significantly to bureaucratic apathy and citizens' disenchantment with the administration. Since evolution of New Public Administration (NPA), administrative reforms drawing upon the concept of Emotional Intelligence (EI), initiated repositioning administrative effectiveness beyond technical competence and rule compliance, emphasizing emotional awareness, empathy, self-regulation, and social skills as critical administrative capabilities. This was institutionalised through policy reforms focusing upon role of administration not only as regulator but a facilitator to institutionalise public engagement in service delivery without losing the ultimate essence.

An attempt has been made through an integrative theoretical analysis to bridge classical bureaucracy, bounded rationality, and contemporary governance paradigms with EI theory, demonstrating how emotionally intelligent administrators are better equipped to mitigate apathy, enhance citizen-centric service delivery, and rebuild institutional trust among citizens. The study uses illustrative examples from public service delivery contexts particularly street-level bureaucracy in order to highlights how deficits in emotional intelligence exacerbate exclusion, delay, and discretionary misuse, whereas emotionally competent administrative practices foster responsiveness, ethical discretion, and collaborative governance. Simultaneously the study proposes an institutional framework like “*Mission Karmayogi*” for embedding emotional intelligence within public administration through recruitment, training, performance appraisal, and leadership development.

The paper provides insights and contributes to public administration theory by humanising the state administrative ecosystem and offers policy-relevant insights for administrative reforms aimed at reducing apathy and improving democratic governance outcomes just by inculcating sense of responsiveness in impulsive behavioural patterns.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence (EI), Administrative Apathy, Public Administration, Bureaucracy, Governance, Street-Level Bureaucracy (SLB)

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1. INTRODUCTION

For ages individuals generally tend to react impulsively based on their emotional instincts, often disregarding the uncertain outcomes that may arise. This brings forth a complicated issue regarding how to maintain control and exhibit authentic emotional responses. Emotion is a spontaneous response to internal mental stimuli which reflects the personal reaction to a thing or behaviour. Emotions involves sudden onset of mental activity such as joy, sorrow, lust, hate and love. Emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to understand and manage your own emotions, as well as recognize and influence the emotions of those around you. This is generally in response to the social environmental variables. The term "Emotional Intelligence" is often termed as contradictory in pair due to both having different notions to handle a situation. Someone being dubbed as "emotional" creates a sense of behaviour influenced by unfolding stimuli inside a body that may not be rational at the moment. This is not restricted to people having lower IQ only (Intelligence Quotient) in fact, people with higher IQ or capacity may result in obscure decision making process due to lack of emotional intelligence. As "emotional intelligence" is the skill or capacity to perceive and rationally manage our own emotions for optimal decisions making process.

There are several examples when people at prestigious level and with higher IQ tends to involve in irrational and immoral acts only due to lack of control over their own emotions. At general population level we have plethora of instances when a trivial issues in society results in serious conflicts or crime. This doesn't mean human should strictly repress their emotions. In fact acknowledging one's emotional instability and learning from experience to better use in the situation could enhance existing social relationships. However, it is conjectured that people with higher IQ tends to secure much more success than people having better command over their emotions. But the several research results shows that people at work have much more appealing and possess outstanding success in their professions due to better management of emotions. A person having skill of persuasion, communication, leadership and empathy to others, are in the higher level of emotional intelligence. They know about their weaknesses with emotions simultaneously they have ability to reckon others responsive behaviour. It is quite popular in the management and basic norms among civil servants that "overtness to all emotions and the ability to regulate your own emotions and the emotions of others add up in facilitating growth and insight.

Daniel Goleman's book "Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ" helped popularize the idea of emotional intelligence in 1995. Researchers John Mayer and Peter Salovey first used the phrase around 1990, but psychologist Daniel Goleman later made it widely known. Emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in people's lives, particularly in occupations that require a lot of commitment and effort. Due to the sensitivity required in the field of administrative services, the use of emotional intelligence assumes significance. Lower emotional intelligence can result in a number of potential pitfalls that can impact relationships and work, among other aspects of life. Less emotional maturity is associated with more disputes, poorer relationships, and ineffective emotional coping. It can be used to forecast a person's potential academic performance. You can hide your true feelings when you are skilled at managing your own emotions. When you understand how others are feeling, you can appeal to their emotions and influence them to take actions against their own best interests. There is no correlation

between IQ and EI scores. In other words, the ability to understand and manage one's own and others' emotions has nothing to do with IQ. This makes complete sense because we've all encountered intelligent individuals who, despite their intelligence, lacked social skills.

These measurements, along with personality, make up a person's psyche. IQ and emotional intelligence make an effort to measure various aspects of human intelligence. Emotional intelligence is the only aspect of the human psyche that can be developed and improved through learning new skills. In the end, having a high EI means having the potential to boost team productivity, have significantly improved interpersonal relationships, and have a higher success rate in achieving goals. Unlike IQ, emotional intelligence is something that people can actually develop if they know how. Everyone is aware that intelligence doesn't equate to virtue, success, or happiness, but up until the development of emotional intelligence, we didn't know why.

Daniel Goleman's remarkable report of psychology and neuroscience gives stunning new insights into our "two minds" the rational and the emotional and how they combine to decide our fate. Effective emotional intelligence must start at the individual level. You cannot distill or improve the growth, well-being, and sense of self of others without first understanding your own emotional behavior. Leaders are often identified by their emotional intelligence, and it is these skills that help to create a more productive work environment. Emotionally intelligent people understand their own limitations.

2. ADMINISTRATIVE APATHY AS A GOVERNANCE CRISIS

In the decolonization era welfare states across the globe has adopted policies to ensure equal society, and across many societies, governments operate a range of welfare and assistance programmes intended to support vulnerable populations such as economically disadvantaged groups, indigenous populations, and victims of natural or man-made disasters. These programmes aim to mitigate multidimensional poverty and deliver essential services including nutrition, healthcare, shelter, and education, with the overarching objective of improving the quality of life of those facing structural disadvantages. However the policies are meant to provide aspirational goals, nonetheless objectives determined by such initiatives, often missed the humane treatment and their implementation frequently have limited success due to persistent administrative inefficiencies at the level of service delivery.

In fact one of the most commonly cited concerns relates to the conduct and attitudes of officials responsible for programme/service delivery (called the face of policies), who often exhibit apathy, insensitivity, or a paternalistic behaviour towards beneficiaries. Unaware of the ill-effects, such attitudes not only undermine service delivery but also intensify the hardships faced by already marginalized communities who have been excluded from governance. These administrative shortcomings stem from multiple interrelated factors, including commonly exemplified rigid bureaucratic procedures, insufficient professional training, and chronic resource constraints, all of which limit the capacity of welfare systems to function effectively.

Indian public administration has always faced criticism for administrative apathy towards service delivery. In the execution of welfare state policies, the effectiveness of social assistance programmes is shaped not only by policy design but also by the behavioural orientation of

frontline administrators who gives ultimate life to policy goals. This can be substantiated from the framework of 'Street-Level Bureaucracy' (Michael Lipsky), frontline officials such as ration dealers, Anganwadi Workers, health workers, and local revenue officials who exercise significant discretion in the implementation of schemes like the Public Distribution System (PDS), Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA), Ayushman Bharat, and National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP) and many more which are directly related to inclusive growth of society. With this vast discretionary power, when combined with weak institutional accountability and limited emotional competencies, combined with lack of awareness among targeted beneficiaries often translates into administrative apathy rather than empathetic service delivery.

This is reflected in the empirical observations made in multiple Comptroller and Auditor General of India (CAG) audit reports which highlight recurring gaps between policy goals and intent and resulting ground-level outcomes. Commonly audits of food security schemes and employment programmes repeatedly point to problems like exclusion errors, ghost beneficiaries, delayed payments, procedural rigidity, and inadequate grievance redressal mechanisms. Administrative responses mark these failures but are commonly attributed to logistical or technical shortcomings; however a deeper examination reveals the role of attitudinal deficits among street-level bureaucrats, including indifference towards beneficiaries, procedural dominance over human need, and behavioural neglect of vulnerable populations.

Looking from an Emotional Intelligence perspective, the absence of empathy, self-awareness, and social sensitivity among implementing officials exacerbates these governance failures. Scheme beneficiaries particularly the poor, elderly, women, and marginalized communities including people from SCs and STs of society only interact with the state at moments of acute vulnerability. Accordingly to CAG findings these engagements during service delivery indicate that administrative interactions are frequently characterized by insensitivity, lack of communication, and coercive compliance requirements, suggesting a deficit of emotional competence within bureaucratic practice involving the SLBs (Table 1). These experiences become the ultimate face of public administration among citizens. Resultant, this reinforces a culture where compliance with rules takes precedence over responsiveness to citizen needs and empathy towards them. The concept of administrative apathy further helps to explain how hierarchical bureaucratic structures normalize emotional disengagement among SLBs and the citizens. Overall ecology turns grey where a negative behavioural pattern remains the genuine response. Through such systems, officials and civil servants are incentivized to minimize risk, adhere strictly to procedures, and prioritize upward accountability over citizen-centric outcomes ultimately giving the dissonance in work culture and an inefficient administration. As reported in audit reports and scholarly findings across schemes such as MGNREGA and social pension programmes, this leads to delayed entitlements, mechanical verification processes, and weak ownership of service outcomes. Beneficiaries are consequently reduced to case numbers rather than rights-bearing citizens.

Table 1: *Source CAG Audit reports*

Scheme	Street-Level Bureaucrats (SLBs)	Observed EI Deficit	CAG Audit Findings (Indicative)	Administrative Outcome
Public Distribution System (PDS) / NFSA	Fair Price Shop dealers, Supply Inspectors	Low empathy; patronizing behavior; poor communication with beneficiaries	Exclusion of eligible households, diversion of food grains, weak grievance redressal, irregular inspections	Food insecurity persists; erosion of trust; beneficiaries treated as passive recipients
MGNREGA	Gram Rozgar Sevaks, Panchayat Secretaries, Block officials	Emotional detachment; rule-bound rigidity; low responsiveness	Delayed wage payments, unmet demand for work, inadequate social audits	Distress employment fails to act as safety net; normalization of procedural injustice
National Social Assistance Programme (Old-age/Widow Pension)	Revenue officials, Block Development Officers	Lack of sensitivity to elderly and widows; bureaucratic aloofness	Delays in sanction and disbursement, incomplete beneficiary records	Heightened vulnerability of elderly; welfare perceived as charity not entitlement
Ayushman Bharat – PMJAY	Hospital administrators, frontline health staff	Weak interpersonal skills; low accountability towards patients	Denial of cashless treatment, poor beneficiary awareness, uneven empanelment	Health entitlements undermined; exclusion of poorest households
ICDS (Anganwadi Services)	Anganwadi Workers & Supervisors	Burnout-induced apathy; limited emotional engagement	Gaps in nutrition delivery, irregular monitoring, infrastructure deficiencies	Child malnutrition persists despite scheme expansion
Mid-Day Meal Scheme / PM POSHAN	School heads, cooks, local education officials	Procedural compliance over child welfare	Quality lapses, irregular supply, weak inspection mechanisms	Nutritional and educational objectives diluted
PM Awas Yojana (Rural/Urban)	Local engineers, municipal officials	Insensitivity to housing precarity; mechanical verification	Ineligible beneficiary misidentification, incomplete houses, fund delays	Housing insecurity continues; beneficiary dissatisfaction

In whole if taken together, the intersection of Street-Level Bureaucracy with low Emotional Intelligence, and entrenched administrative apathy institutionalised within middle to bottom level administrative ecology provides a compelling explanation for why welfare delivery in India often falls short despite expansive policy frameworks and fiscal commitments. In fact the targeted scheme which is in action for about five decades doesn't result into overall goals. This as per CAG reports serve as critical institutional evidence of these systemic shortcomings,

underscoring that governance failures are not merely administrative but fundamentally relational and behavioural. Addressing these challenges therefore requires reforms that go beyond procedural streamlining to include emotional competence training, accountability for frontline behavior, and a reorientation of welfare administration toward dignity-based, human-centered governance.

3. CONCEPTUALISING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE: FROM PSYCHOLOGY TO GOVERNANCE

E.L. Thorndike's (1920) social intelligence and Gardner's (1983) intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligences are the foundations of emotional intelligence. Prior to Salovey and Mayer's 1990 proposal of the construct's first formal description and model, the word EI itself was addressed multiple times in the literature. Several different ideas quickly followed this early model (e.g. Bar-On, 1997; Mayer & Salovey, 1997). Emotional intelligence integrates emotions with intelligence, perceiving emotions as valuable sources of information for navigating social environments. A formal definition of emotional intelligence was put forth by Salovey and Mayer (1990, p. 189): "The ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings, to discriminate among them, and to use this information to guide one's thinking and action." Mayer and Salovey (1997) expanded the term to include four different but linked abilities: perceiving, using, understanding, and managing emotions.

Goleman (1995) was the driving force behind the field's development. Emotional intelligence involves recognizing one's own feelings, being aware of others' feelings, distinguishing between them, and applying this knowledge to influence one's thinking, behavior, and decision-making. American psychologist and author Daniel Goleman (1995) who is globally regarded as the founder of emotional intelligence classified the concept into four categories and maintains that the model is applicable to organizational development and personal development. According to Goleman and Rahim (2002), emotional intelligence is the ability to organize our own feelings and those of others, to motivate ourselves, and to manage emotions effectively in ourselves and in our relationships. Martinez (1997) asserts that a variety of non-cognitive abilities, competencies, and skills affect a person's capacity to handle the demands and stresses of their surroundings.

Several scholars have conceptualized the EI in various ways, prominent among were Zeng and Miller (2001) who noted that despite the widespread interest in emotional intelligence and its potential benefits in the workplace, EI was still elusive form human resource management. According to them, diversity in psychometric qualities was caused by operational differences in emotional intelligence and its underlying theory. However, behavioural sciences failed to push this notion in administrative capability. According to Goleman, Boyatzis, and Mckee (2002), emotional intelligence, or synonymous with Emotional Quotient (EQ), is twice as crucial for professions at all levels as technical skills and IQ. As a result, emotional intelligence competencies are becoming increasingly relevant at higher levels, particularly in universities, where academic administrators play a key role in the administrative function. Martinez (1997) identified a range of non-cognitive talents, capabilities, and competencies that impact one's ability to cope with environmental demands and stresses. According to Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso (2007), Keltner and Haidt (2001), and Brackett et al. (2006), emotional intelligence encompasses the capacity to

accurately and adaptively perceive, assess, and express emotion; comprehend emotion and emotional knowledge; access and generate feelings to support cognitive activities and adaptive action; and regulate emotions in oneself and others. As a result, social interactions and verbal-nonverbal cues can be used to understand people's intentions, ideas, and behaviors.

Nonetheless Goleman (2001) asserted that the field of work and organizational success can directly benefit from an EI-based theory of performance, especially when it comes to forecasting excellence in a variety of occupations, from leadership to sales. According to him, a fundamental set of ideas unites all of these EI models. To Goleman “Emotional intelligence encompasses the ability to recognize and control emotions in both oneself and others” and Self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management are the four basic EI domains suggested by this most condensed formulation. One of Goleman's emotional intelligence aspects, self-management or self-regulation, refers to the capacity to control one's own emotions and impulses, to remain composed amid harmful circumstances, and to remain calm regardless of one's feelings. It focuses on the capacity to self-monitor, adapt, or modify behavior in response to external circumstances. This crucial emotional competency enables people in leadership roles to manage their emotions and impulses rather than letting them overwhelm them. Emotional control, goal-achieving motivation, flexibility, and regular initiative are all key components of self-management.

4. DOMINANT ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN ADMINISTRATION

In public administration, emotional intelligence (EI) is based on both cognitive intelligence or reasoning and a methodical comprehension of emotions and moods. It comprises of various stakeholders' specialized ability to recognize feelings and emotions in their immediate work environment, but it also incorporates other qualities that can develop individuals with higher emotional intelligence. These people's emotional resources and abilities become extremely important and powerful when they actively participate in the production or consumption of public goods, and they may have an impact on the results of public organizations. Similarly, emotional public administration refers to the emotions of public administration stakeholders that represent their reactions to changes in the environment and include specific experiences, cognitions, bodily sensations, and assessments of the current situation.

As Vigoda & Meisler (2010) enforces that public administration and public policy rely on people's actions and decisions to connect the mind and heart. The daily acts of government and agencies at all levels, whether federal, state, or local, involve both the mind and the heart, despite potential conflicts in aspirations, analysis, and interpretations. To them scholars should explore innovative ways to integrate knowledge from the heart, including feelings, emotions, and attachments, rather than relying just on logic, rationality, and facts. Emotional public administration refers to stakeholders' emotional reactions to environmental changes, including their experiences, cognitions, bodily sensations, and assessments of the situation. Rourke (1992) defines intelligent public administration as the ability to solve problems through abstract reasoning about power and influence in organizations (politics), logical and organized actions (bureaucratic order and managerial knowledge), systematic learning of targeted materials (policy making), and responsiveness to stakeholder needs.

Therefore, emotionally intelligent public administration is capable of comprehending and resolving issues that are important to large numbers of citizens as well as policy matters that are governed, managed, or overseen by governments. Vigoda & Meisler (2010) expands the list of these skills which encompasses a number of areas, including (1) controlling the emotional reactions of public stakeholders; (2) comprehending emotions and the emotional meanings of others (citizens, clients, employees, etc.); (3) evaluating emotions in diverse contexts; (4) utilizing emotion in reason-based decisions and policy making; and (5) recognizing emotions in faces, voices, postures, and other human forms of expression during public management activities.

Inadequate accountability, a lack of transparency, a weak organizational structure, lack of responsiveness, inefficiencies, and low motivation are all potential threats to good governance. The emotional intelligence index is the reverse of these. Therefore, emotional intelligence training ought to be provided to government personnel in order to improve their performance. The only equivalent of good governance is emotional intelligence, which includes, among other qualities, integrity, transparency, self-control, self-respect, empathy, self-awareness, initiative, and accountability. Levitats and Vigoda-Gadot (2020, p. 434) explains that people with high emotional intelligence (EI) are better able to comprehend another person's perspective, accurately identify with another's emotions, experience the same or another appropriate emotion in response to them, and to act on this internal experience with empathy. Therefore, the ability to identify the emotions of others aids in understanding how to react emotionally (O'Boyle Jr. et al., 2011).

Eshuis et al. (2023) found in their study that the capacity to appraise others' emotions predicts improved performance can be explained by the fact that an accurate appraisal of inspectees (SLBs) emotions assists inspectors in responding correctly, creating a cooperative environment, and avoiding confrontation. The conclusion also emphasizes how inspectors' use of emotions to boost happiness and motivation enhances their ability to complete regulatory tasks. To their surprise, study also discovered that two elements of EI, emotional assessment of self and emotion control, had no relationship with regulatory performance. One possible explanation is that simply perceiving and comprehending one's own emotions has only an indirect impact on SLBs' interactions during inspections, whereas interactions with others (inspectees) affect interactions directly and are thus critical to inspector performance. They term this as dimensional effects of EI on job performance.

5. 'MISSION KARMAYOGI': Era Of Transformation In Indian Administration

The Government of India launched the National Programme for Civil Services Capacity Building ('NPCSCB') - "Mission Karmayogi" with the objective of enhancing governance through Civil Services Capacity-Building program in September 2020. This national initiative uses a cutting-edge digital platform to transform capacity building. It heralds an era which marks shift from "rule-based" to "role-based", "linking training and development" to "competencies", continuous learning opportunities at every level and not just senior levels.

Mission Karmayogi was introduced as a complete gateway that incorporates cutting-edge learning technology to provide government workers with easy access to a wide range of interactive tools, resources, and training modules. This digital ecosystem helps public servants improve their knowledge, skills, and competences online, helping them to excel in their roles. Prominence of Mission Karmayogi' lies in its adaptive learning architecture, which customizes

information according to individual learning preferences and professional needs, is its primary innovation. This individualized approach improves learning effectiveness and encourages a culture of continual development and professional advancement for government officials.

The mission comprises of six pillars: (i) policy framework; (ii) institutional framework; (iii) competency framework; (iv) digital learning framework (integrated government online training Karmayogi platform; iGOT-Karmayogi); (v) electronic Human Resource Management System (e-HRMS); (vi) programme management unit (PMU) to provide program management and support services and (vii) monitoring and evaluation (M&E) framework. The Prime Minister's Public Human Resource Council (PMHRC), the mission's apex body, provides strategic direction and drives policy reforms and capacity building; the Cabinet Secretariat Coordination Unit monitors NPCSCB implementation, aligns stakeholders, and provides a mechanism for overseeing capacity building plans (CBPs); the Capacity Building Commission (CBC) provides functional supervision of training institutions and facilitates the preparation of annual CBPs; the Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) owns all the digital assets developed for NPCSCB.

Civil service training in India has traditionally followed strict standards and protocols. This platform promotes a unified and responsive administrative framework by allowing for peer learning, collaboration, and knowledge sharing across boundaries. It directs the shift to dynamic, role-based learning frameworks from conventional, rule-based training paradigms is a key component of the CBC's approach. As governance becomes more complicated, it's important to equip public servants with competences that fit with their positions and responsibilities. The development of multifaceted abilities, such as strategic thinking, leadership, decision-making, and stakeholder management, is emphasized by role-based training and involvement. This method equips public servants to handle a variety of challenges by placing learning objectives within the particular requirements of professional roles difficulties with effectiveness and agility.

6. CONCLUSION

Street-level bureaucrats differ from the classic Weberian bureaucracy because they are in direct contact with citizens at the frontline of government and exercise discretion in deciding who receives assistance and who does not. If looking it through cost-benefit analysis, street-level bureaucrats as rational actors who strive to maximize their "utility." However, this utility is not limited to personal self-interest but also includes values such as reducing work-related stress, achieving professional goals, serving needy citizens, and effectively implementing sound public policies. Vigoda & Meisler (2010) study suggests that modern public organizations often overlook the emotional aspects of administrative operations in their pursuit of reason and effectiveness. They vindicated this proposition as neglect in public administration theory and writing about feelings, emotions, and emotional intelligence is a clear indicator. Hassan et al. (2023) establishes that understanding the negative consequences of depression, anxiety, and stress on discretion emphasizes the importance of organizations prioritizing mental health support for street-level officials. According to them this can be accomplished through employee support programs, mental health training, and access to counseling services.

In these contexts 'Mission Karmayogi' heralds an era of administrative ecosystem which persistently trains civil servants at every level with their customized demands of emotional intelligence framework and simultaneously equipping them with effective skillsets. Organizations can improve street-level bureaucrats' decision-making quality and overall work performance by investing in mental health support. In fact the favorable influence of Empathic Resonance on discretion implies that creating a supportive work atmosphere that promotes empathy, trust, and emotional intelligence is critical for making smart decisions. Emotional intelligence-focused training programs, team-building activities, and organizational and employee transparency and trust-building policies can all help with this.

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